

IMPACT OF INFLATION ON STANDARD OF LIVING OF HOUSEHOLDS IN GUWAHATI, ASSAM

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Abstract : This study has been undertaken to observe the potential impact of inflation on the standard of living of the population in Guwahati, Assam. Inflation being a prominent phenomenon in every economy, casts multifaceted impacts on the various agents of the economy impacting the overall living standard of the population. To obtain the requisite potential outcomes, the presence of inflation has to be established first, which was carried out by analysing the price indices for a given time period extracted from secondary sources, indicating the positive presence of inflation. Once that the presence of inflation has been established, subsequently, the indicators of the standard of living was evaluated, which were sourced from conduction of an empirical study. Following the analysis of the parameters, viz, income, expenditure and availability of domestic amenities, it could be profoundly concluded that, inflation significantly impacted income and expenditure negatively, however, availability of domestic amenities indicated positive outcomes. Comprehensively, it could be established that households were indeed hit hard by inflation, despite of which, they could successfully retain their living standards in terms of basic amenities. However simultaneously, in the attempts of retaining their access to domestic amenities, they were exempted from affording luxuries which halted their standard of living at a stagnated level, ceasing them to further push forward.

Index Terms – Living standard, inflation, Guwahati

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflation, a crucial economic index, profoundly influences India's diverse population. It's the rate at which the general price level of goods and services rises, dwindling the purchasing power of money. As defined by the International Monetary Fund, "inflation is the rate of increase in prices over a given period of time. Inflation is typically a broad measure, such as the overall increase in prices or the increase in the cost of living in a country."

Taking the context of a complex economy like that of India, inflation is one of the most influencing factors that in many ways influences and determines the average standard of living of its population. However, it is worth mentioning that, inflation as an influencing factor determining the overall status of a country's economy, is not just a phenomena occurring and influencing just the Indian economy solely. It is indeed a phenomenon that is often a nightmare to tackle, if went out of control, for the entire world as a global economy. On a global scale, analytics indicate of how from Pakistan to US, Australia to Germany, the cost of living is a rising to new highs and causing new hardships. This vividly indicates how the inflation as an influencing phenomenon for an economy is becoming a threat to be tackled for the entire world as a whole or individually under varying circumstances. Focusing on the United States, it is stated that "Price rises have hit everyone but Inflation hits poorer Americans hardest. The lowest earning fifth of Americans already spend 83% of their income on housing, according to labor department's consumer expenditure survey and can ill afford increases in rents, let alone fuel, food and other essentials." (The Guardian, 2022). Here, it is purely reflected that inflation is hitting the American economy hard, which is the world's largest economy. Though, there are various different types of inflation influencing the economy, the overall impact is nothing but a mixed outcome of all the different types of inflation functioning together. It's consequences, as it is further elaborated in the research, covers a wide range of concerns and issues some of which are quite alarming for the economy as a whole. However, for any economy, it's central bank and the Government plays a vital role in regulating Inflation to the best so as to reduce hardships of its people and also to ensure that the Growth pace of the economy doesn't remain stranded owing to absence of Inflation. It is to be noted that, though Inflation as a phenomenon is a nightmare in its excessive presence, it's also a nightmare in cases of its pure absence as it leaves the economy vulnerable to ever slowing paces of growth and in worst scenarios, a complete collapse. Thus, cutting out a perfect balance between the presence and absence of inflation, to prevent both Economic hardships or Stagnation of Economy, is a salient task for a country's central bank and government. However. As present scenarios indicate, Stagnation of economy is nothing as a concern for the Indian Economy or for the global economy, as Inflation rates are already soaring above the required levels, thus threatening Economic Hardships indeed. If the concept of economic hardships is elaborated, then one of the most influenced and

impacted aspect of an economy is the standard of living of the population of the country which play an important role as a vital economic agent of an economy. A high rate of inflation severely impacts the purchasing power of the population which in turn impacts its standard of living. However, analysing the impact of inflation on the standard of living of the population is not an easy task, as there is an absence of any direct statistical or mathematical relation between rising costs and standard of living. Moreover, the concept of Standard of Living is itself too broad to analyse as a uniform entity without missing out on any of its vital aspect. Thus, we are to consider some of the most prominent, Significant and eligible parameters that shall effectively denote the concept of Standard Of living, and the effect and outcome of the impact that inflation casts on these parameters shall in turn vividly reflect the impact on standard of living itself. With regards to this particular research work, the Parameters that have been taken into account are Income, Expenditure and availability of basic amenities. Thus, the observation of the analysis of the Impact of inflation on Income, expenditure and availability of basic amenities via elaborated Statistical approaches forms the core foundation of this Empirical study with special emphasis on the targeted area of West Guwahati.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Inflation, which is the elevation in general price level, is one of the most flamboyant factors impacting the standard of living. Our study that aims at studying this relation, is however not the first attempt in doing so. There exist many such literatures, who too attempts to establish the relation between inflation and standard of living, while taking into consideration, the numerous aspects of Inflation and its impact on the living standards of the population. Thus, reviewing them reveals the multi-dimensional face of inflation, that operates in an economy.

2.1 Analysing literature focused on international contexts.

The Phenomena of Inflation is something whose presence can be observed typically in every functioning economy, in an international context. With context to Turkey, a study by Bozkurt, Quartz & Schneider (2022), aimed at examining the influence of inflation on the cost of living among urban residents in Turkey. Through a simple random sampling technique and a descriptive research design approach, notable conclusions were stated with regards to the nature of impact of Inflation on the cost of Living of the population of turkey. Following the analysis, it was stated, *“inflation had increased the cost of living. The high cost of living makes poor people extra vulnerable. Inflation positively and significantly affects the cost of living. The increase in inflation increases the cost of living.”* (Bozkurt, Quartz & Schneider, 2022). This statement vividly states the influential nature of Inflation with regards to cost of Living, which is established by the support of the results obtained by operation of admissible and appropriate statistical and mathematical approaches on the collected empirics. However, the point here that requires and demands a special attention is the overall nature of the influence of inflation, which is strictly a positive relation with regards to cost of living, i.e., with an increase in Inflation, cost of living also increases. However, a limitation can be observed in the study, which is to a small extent, the confined nature of the study, wherein the potential and possible impact of inflation on standard of living was overlooked. However, this limitation is considerable, as the overall study by default, was aimed solely at observing the impact on cost of living, and the aspect of standard of living was not explicitly mentioned or focused upon. Now deviating to other countries, studies have been performed on similar grounds, following similar yet diverse approaches and aiming to observe a similar objective. For example, with regards to Pakistan, study by Farid, Khan & Warriach (2012), aiming to study the effect of Inflation on Standard of living of people residing in Multan, taking into consideration, the analysis of factors like saving, loan possibility, income, recreation, expenses etc as the vital indicators of Standard of living. This study holds a significant uniqueness with regards to its aim, as it focuses to establish a relationship between inflation and its impact on standard of living, rather than analysing the impact on cost of living, which is the usual conventional focus. The point here that is to be noted is that, inflation casts a significant influence on the standard of living of the middle class, and operates as a factor of creation of economic burden on the masses thus degrading their overall standard of living. Apart from impacting the Standard and cost of living of the population, inflation has great potentials to cast damages or in worst cases, cause disasters on an aggregate scale. It greatly hinders economy growth of any economy if uncontrolled. A high inflation rate poses a threat to economic growth, diminishing individuals' purchasing power and subsequently raising living costs. Enhanced economic growth has the potential to alleviate the burden of living expenses (Ojonugwa, Ogasheko & Ezekiel, 2024).

2.2 Analysing literature focused on Indian context.

With regards to India, the nature of impact of Inflation is not something Heterogenous or unusually distinct. Literatures reveal the occurrence of a similar influence of inflation on the various elements of the economy as a whole. . If it increase with high rate then it become disaster for the respective economy (Zafar, Hmedat, Babiker, 2016). Another significant aspect in which inflation casts noticeable influence is on the overall spending power of Households. It is stated that, *“The empirical findings of this study complement the economic theories and evidences that inflation also increases the cost of living, price of commodities and reduces the opportunities of getting goods jobs. This situation directly influences households' income and their spending capacities.”* (Sulekha, Mary, Tharmalingam, 2019) . This is a significant impact as Household forms an important sector of an economy, and the spending incurred by it holds a significant position in contributing to the smooth running of the entire economic cycle. Thus, any hinderance in this mechanism threatens to impact the entire cycle as a whole leading to aggregative consequences. However, it is worth noting that inflation tends to have somewhat a positive impact on the economy. In this context, *“Inflation is essential to the economy even though it decreases consumer purchasing power and leads to a mismatch between supply and demand. A rise in demand for goods and services will lead to inflation, which will boost output and aid in the expansion of the economy.”* (Jayalakshmi, Jayachitra, Yasodha, 2023) , suitably captures and conveys the boosting and accelerating nature of Inflation, although the limit of the same is to be carefully controlled and regulated so as to obtain the desired results.

In conclusion, the study of various appropriate and significant literatures revealed the two fold impact of inflation in an economy where in on one hand inflation is a necessary phenomenon to continue the rolling of the cycle of development in an economy while it cast much more significant and disastrous impact in case that it goes uncontrolled and unregulated. These results were concluded after prolonged and thorough analysis of various data, with aids of advanced and sophisticated statistical tools

leading to almost accurate and reliable results. Further, it can be vividly observed that the conclusions derived by the literatures were homogenous in nature stating the negative relation between inflation and Standard of living. Also, a significant point to be noted is that, most of the literatures primarily or often solely focused upon the potential impact of inflation on cost of living, and either completely or partially ignoring the influence on standard of living, thus leaving inadequate attention being levied upon this specific aspect. Other miscellaneous studies have been performed on other regions of the country, but no significant, broad or remarkable studies have been performed for our considered target area with regards to our specific concerned topic, which leaves for us an opportunity to extend the ocean of research with specialised limelight on our targeted area. Thus, our study aims at concentrating on the west Guwahati region of Guwahati city, Kamrup (M), Assam, India to perform our research bearing the objective, *To examine the impact of inflation on Standard of Living via analysis of a diverse basket of factors and their interrelation.*

3. AREA OF STUDY

The area of study as opted for the purpose of collecting data to serve as the basis of the research, is the area of west Guwahati as a portion representing the entire Guwahati city as a whole. However, it is made sure that the area chosen, gives a fair reflection of the entire city if even if not at a pin point accuracy. For further vivid reference, the Map can be presented as below:

FIG 1.1 : Map of Guwahati

Since our study primarily focuses on the Standard of living with respect to rising cost of living specifically, the analysis and study of the numerous diverse aspects of the city becomes purely secondary. Thus, prime focus has been laid on the study of the income structure of the population of the city as obtained from trusted sources. It has been found that, Average salary in Guwahati is **1,185,013 INR** per year. The most typical earning is **998,256 INR**. All data are based on **42** salary surveys. Salaries are different between men and women. Men receive an average salary of **1,264,457 INR**. Women receive a salary of **831,880 INR**. The most paid careers are Health Care & Medical with average income **2,736,885 INR** and Management & Business with income **1,713,672 INR**. Based on education, the highest salaries receive people with Doctorate Degree with salary of **2,437,408 INR**. The second most paid education level is Bachelor's Degree with salary of **1,147,994 INR**. Different experiences affect earning as well. People with 20+ Years of experience receive salary of **2,420,770 INR**. Employees with 16-20 Years of experience receive **1,780,223 INR**.

(Source : [Guwahati | Average Salary Survey 2024](#))

Thus, with this pre requisite data and knowledge, for executing further analysis, further primary data has been collected and analysed so as to obtain relevant results and the same can be cross checked for abnormally higher variations.

4. METHODOLOGY

This research paper aims to explain how the rising cost of living is influencing the standard of living of the people of west Guwahati.

For research purpose there is a use of both quantitative approach for facts and data driven research and qualitative research methodology for surveys to identify the trends over time. secondary data is also used along with primary data with necessary precautions to avoid any possible sampling errors being undertaken. To serve the purpose of analysing the collected data for deriving appropriate results, the statistical software SPSS has been utilised to perform and compute statistical operations. They included utilization of appropriate graphs & tables and a diverse range of descriptive statistic measures.

(NOTE: All the statistical analysis including the diagrams has been strictly executed through the usage of SPSS- 26 software only.

5. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

It is a pre- established fact that in any economy, inflation is something which is a very usual and prominent phenomena, which is indeed one of the major factors that influences the standard of living of the population of any economy. The Indian economy being a very rapid growing economy, is facing an annual inflation level of around 5.62% . However, to obtain a more clear and vivid image of the scenario and status of cost of living in the country, it is vital to observe and analyse the aggregate trend that has been prevailing over the span of last 5 years. This shall convey a much legit ruling about the past scenario of inflation and the potential expectations for the future. For this we shall utilise the data as provided by the statistical handbook of Assam throughout the years 2018 to 2021. With the assistance of the source as obtained, the data particularly focusing on the price indices, viz. CPI and WPI has been extracted, with base year as 2001. It is further being tabulated and presented through a diagrammatic approach so as to make the observations more vivid and precise.

TABLE 1.1 : CPI & WPI for Respective Periods

SL.no	Period	CPI	WPI
1.	2018	255	384
2.	2019	281	423
3.	2020	319	435
4.	2021	347	431

From the above table it can be observed that, throughout the years; 2018 to 2021, the CPI had increased from 255 to all the way to 347 which is a sheer indication that the prices of the necessary basket of goods have observed significant increases. Also, if the WPI values are observed, it too has increased from 384 to 435 through 2018 and 2020. However, from the transition to 2021 from 2020, the WPI has registered a fall from 435 to 431. Nevertheless, analysing the reason of this does not fall under the scope of this study and thus, it shall be ignored for the same.

FIG 2.1 : CPI & WPI line Graph

Departing away from the figures, if we tend to observe the trends of the changing price indices, it can be vividly observed from the above diagram that both the price indices, that is; the CPI and the WPI have registered significant increases over the period of time. Now in concluding terms, it can be stated that the prices of the basket of goods that is considered under the CPI and WPI has increased over the years thus indicating towards the presence of a significant rate of inflation in the economy.

(Source : Statistical Handbook of Assam, Edition : 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022)

Now that, it is established that Inflation is an obvious phenomenon common to almost every functioning active economies including India, it is now vital to determine the scale of impact of Inflation, if any, on the domestic economy. For the purpose, we are to primarily examine the influence and impact of Inflation on the income of the population in real terms, apart from the changes in its nominal aspects, that shall be observed later on if necessary. The conducted empirical survey focuses on all the vital indicators that shall potentially reveal the scale of impact of inflation on the common masses. The outcome of the survey is processed so as to obtain the same through a diagrammatical approach for a more vivid and clear understanding, and the same is presented below:

FIG 2.1

FIG 2.2

FIG 2.3

FIG 2.4

FIG 2.5

FIG 2.6

The Diagrams provide a comprehensible image of the potential impact of inflation on income of the sample population and accessibility of vital necessities of everyday life. Focusing on the Income aspect of the samples, for the income to cope up with rising inflation, it should increase simultaneously with inflation (in nominal terms) at an ideal rate so as to keep the real income constant, and not decline with rises in prices in the worst case scenario impacting the purchasing power in a negative manner otherwise. However, to verify if this prevails, the statistics are to be observed. From the data collected, it can be observed that 60% of the samples find their nominal income to increase (Fig 2.2), while 40% don't. However, although a more than half of the samples find a positive increment in their nominal income, the captivating observation is that, about 60% of the samples don't find their augmented income to be adequate in coping up with inflation (Fig 2.1), indicating that their real income has been impacted negatively as the increase in Nominal Income wasn't sufficient to tackle the rising prices and hold their real income constant. This impact on income is also reflected on the other aspects of the sample population's lifestyle. Almost the entire sample population {(98%), Fig 2.3} finds the healthcare costs to have surged over the years and about 66% of them have been significantly affected in terms of their accessibility to healthcare, while only 8% have stated to have been non impacted (Fig 2.5). In terms of necessity goods, the entire sample population finds the prices of necessities to have risen (Fig 2.6). However, a peculiar and rather strange phenomena can be observed here, i.e., although the entire population find the prices of necessities to have risen, only 18% have reduced their goods and services consumption and 8% have remained constant, while astonishingly a huge majority of the population, i.e., 74% have actually increased their consumption (Fig 2.4). This can be attributed to the operation of Demonstration & Ratchet effect, wherein even if the income falls in real terms, the consumption doesn't fall, and instead, increases. The impacts on the Various parameters can be concurrently observed via the following diagram:

FIG: 2.7

The diagram observes the modal responses for the parameters that has been taken into account, where 1 denotes the response “YES” or the positive nature of response and 0 denotes “NO” or the negative nature of response. From the diagram we can simultaneously observe that, for the parameters, Potential Increase in healthcare costs, Potential Impact of inflation on accessibility of healthcare services, Potential increase in prices of necessities and Periodic adjustments of income, the modal response has been “YES”. For parameters, Changes in goods and services consumption pattern and adequacy of income adjustments, the modal response has been “NO”, which effectively and suitably lists our observations. Overall, it can be stated that inflation has been negatively impacting the Income and the related aspects of the sample population.

Now, deviating our focus to the other vital determinant of Standard of living, i.e., expenditure, we are to observe and analyse the impact of inflation on the same. However, expenditure’s direct relation with inflation is majorly explained in terms of fluctuations in purchasing power, which is however, quiet complex to judge, explain and derive via usage of statistical approach, which is the prime methodology for our analysis here. For this reason, a different approach is to be utilised wherein, the primary aim shall lie in determining the most influential connecting factor(s), and the impact of inflation on that factor shall determine and explain the overall effect on expenditure in turn. For the purpose, a Regression analysis has been performed. The model considered is:

$$HE = \alpha + \beta HI + \gamma DR + \delta ED + \phi AG + \epsilon$$

Where, Household Expenditure (HE) is the dependant variable and Household Income (HI), Dependency Ratio(DR), Education (ED) & Age (AG) are independent variables. From the analysis, it can be stated that the model used provide the robust fit with R² equal to 0.650 (which is greater than 0.5). It was found that the respective t values stood at 8.842 , -0.059 , 0.655 & 0.491. Thus, the t-test shows that Household Income (HI) is highly significant at 1% level of significance while the other variables, Dependency Ratio(DR), Education (ED) and Age (AG) are insignificant. Thus, Income is the most significant variable that influences the expenditure of the sample population. Moreover, the value of Pearson’s correlation coefficient between them, in 2018 & 2023 stood at 0.753 and 0.803, which indicates the presence of a high degree of positive correlation between them, thus further concreting the relation between them.

Thus, it can be stated that Income holds a significant positive relation with expenditure and is perhaps the most influential factor in determining the trend of expenditure. Thus, analysing the trends of income and expenditure simultaneously shall demonstrate the overall impact of inflation on Expenditure.

Now, the next step of utter importance is to further observe the trends of income and expenditure collectively so as to reveal the outcome and influence of inflation on expenditure over the period of time. For the purpose, the summary / descriptive statistics of the variables are to be observed and analysed. They include, Mean, Median, Mode, Std. Deviation, Variance and Range which are the most important summary statistic and analysing a few of these shall convey sufficient information regarding the trend of these variables. To make the analysis and observation procedure lucid and vivid, the respective values of the descriptive statistics are tabulated with respect to the two time frames. It is presented below:

TABLE 2.1 : Descriptive statistics

Summary Statistics

	Annual Income of Household in 2018 (In Lakhs)	Annual Income of Household in 2023 (In Lakhs)	Annual Expenditure of Household in 2018 (In lakhs)	Annual Expenditure of Household 2023 (In lakhs)
Mean	5.55960	6.74400	3.70752	4.86580
Median	4.50000	6.25000	3.08000	4.85000
Mode	4.000 ^a	8.000	4.000	5.000
Std. Deviation	4.109542	4.439453	2.791376	3.372405
Variance	16.888	19.709	7.792	11.373
Range	19.700	19.650	9.750	14.800

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

The various observations can be stated as follows:

- i. The primary trend that is to be observed is what portion of average income is actually spent by the population. As the value for 2018 is obtained, it indicates that the population spends about 66.67% of its average income. While for 2023, the value is 72.17%. This is about a 5.5% increase. This means that, on an average, the population has increased its relative expenditure with respect to the total percentage of its income. This means that the sample population is relatively ceasing to save to some extent, or put in other way, spending more, which is a possible outcome of inflation, as because inflationary pressures often adversely impact the purchasing power of individuals, inducing them to spend more to maintain their consumption level and pattern.
- ii. Focusing on the averages (Mean) of each variable at each time period, the mean income has increased from about 5.55 Lakhs in 2018 to 6.74 Lakhs in 2023 which is approximately a 21.45% increase. The expenditure on the other hand, had increased from 3.707 Lakhs in 2018 to 4.86 Lakhs in 2023, which is approximately an 31.1%. This demonstrates that the people's expenditure scale is surging at a higher rate with respect to their income surges. In theory, this may be owed to the operation of numerous factors, like shifts in their consumption preferences or other miscellaneous reasons, but in this scenario, the unlikeliness of the operation of the above reasons is quite higher. It is because, if the individual expenses on each essential of an individual's livelihood are observed, then it is found that the entire sample population had found the prices of necessities to have significantly increased as in Fig 2.6, and simultaneously a larger chunk of the population have increased their marginal consumption too as in Fig 2.4 . This led to the increment of the total expenditure as a whole and the prime factor behind this phenomenon is nothing but a high level of inflation.
- iii. The next important summary statistic that is to be observed is the range of the variables. While the increase in range of the income variable is almost negligible at -0.254% , the range of the expenditure variable registers quiet an extensive increment of about 51.8%. It fairly indicates that although the income structure, viz, the Variability and spread of income has remained almost constant, the expense structure of the sample population has significantly transformed. Such a lofty increase in the expenditure range signifies that a major proportion of the sample population has significantly increased their expenses, although their income didn't increase at an adequate scale. This mismatch or dissimilarity is to some extent being fuelled by the soaring levels of inflation, that had impacted the real income of the individuals and are thus forced to spend more to maintain their standard of living.
- iv. Subsequently, the next statistic to focus on is the trend of Standard Deviation of the data so obtained. The Standard deviation of income variable has incremented by 8.03% indicating an increase in income inequality among the sample population as an increasing SD indicates a larger spread of the values, thus conveying the fact that income inequality has surged. However, the change in SD of expenditure is even higher at 20.8%. This indicates that the variation of spending pattern of the population is significantly escalated. This may indicate that while a certain chunk of the population is choosing to either stagnate or reduce their spending, the other portion of the population is increasing their expenditure. This is a peculiarity and can be owed to inflationary pressures as an influential factor in giving rise to such a behaviour.

If the various observations of the trends of income and expenditure is to be concluded, Inflation seems to cast significant impact and influence on the variables and their trends. Primarily, inflation seems to reduce the real income of individuals and thus effect the purchasing power of individuals owing to which they are forced to spend a larger portion of their income in an attempt to maintain their standard of living. Secondly, the expenditure of the households is incrementing at a higher rate as compared to their income, which is not an optimistic observation as the prime rationale behind this is inflation and not any other neutrally impacting factor. Thirdly, the changes in variations of income and expenditure are alarming too as there is an existence of discrepancy between them. All these observations convey that although the expenditure has increased in general, it is primarily due to a fallen purchasing power and a diminishing real income, which is a clear indication of a degradation in the current state of standard of living if the income and spending aspect is taken into consideration.

Now considering the next and the final parameter, i.e. the availability of domestic amenities, its analysis holds utmost importance as domestic amenities form the basis of determination of the status of standard of living and other commodities like luxuries only function as an enhancer and not as the fundamental bedrock of Standard of living. Thus, to analyse if the population holds a certain applaudable state of standard of living, the same shall be conveniently exhibited by the observation of the result of this analysis. For the ease of analysis, the following Graphs are to be observed:

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Electricity

FIG 4.1

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Water for other uses

FIG 4.2

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Drinking Water

FIG 4.3

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Waste Management System

FIG 4.4

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Rain Water Harvesting

FIG 4.5

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Security

FIG 4.6

Pie Chart Count of Availability of Sanitation

FIG 4.7

From the above diagrams, the availability of various domestic facilities can be observed. Electricity is the facility that is uniformly available (Fig 4.1). Focusing on other facilities, Water for other uses (apart from drinking) is available to about 92% of households (Fig 4.2), drinking water to 96% of households (Fig 4.3), Waste management facilities to 88% of them (Fig 4.4), Rainwater harvesting facility to only 20% of households (Fig 4.5), Security to 50% of them (Fig 4.6) and Sanitation to 90% of the households (Fig 4.7). From the data, the majority of the population (More than or equal to 50%) have access to the basic amenities while only rainwater harvesting facility is the least available one. However, this facility is subjected to necessity and potentiality to invest, which is usually prevalent in areas of low water availability and areas lacking public water supply. Thus, scarce availability of this facility may be owed to the fulfilment of the above criterions which eliminates the necessity of procuring this facility. The same can be claimed for security too as it is also a necessity driven facility and not a mandatory or fundamental one. Other than these, most people have access to every vital and basic facility thus eliminating the presence of any alarming situation. Thus, standard of living in terms of Availability of domestic facility, is almost up to the mark with presence of no petrifying peculiarity.

6. CONCLUSION

In concluding terms, if we are to summarise the outcomes of the analysis, upon observing and analysing the three parameters of Standard of living and their changing trends owing to potential influence of inflation, significant results were derived. Focusing on Income as the primary parameter, the soaring inflation rate was aggregately higher on an average, relative to the increment rate of nominal income of the population. This resulted in a falling real income of the sample population, making them worse off and increasing their struggle to maintain their persisting standard of living. The second parameter is to a significant extent affiliated with the first parameter, i.e., Expenditure. The findings reveal an increasing Expenditure of the sample population, which would've been a positive trend if it was due to an increased real income and thus would've been the result of attempts to push their standard of living. However, according to the outcomes of the analysis, this increment in expenditure is not the result of an attempt to push their standard of living, but is a consequence of a struggle to indeed maintain the current status of standard of living owing to ever surging prices. This is further confirmed by the results of the analysis of availability of domestic amenities. Upon prolonged evaluation of the data, it was found that almost every sample household was equipped with the most basic amenities which clearly states that although the population finds the inflation rate to have soared significantly, even with a falling real income, they seem to increase their expenditure to at least maintain their persisting standard of living and equip themselves adequately with the most necessary basic amenities. However, it is not something very optimistic as it ceases them to afford luxuries and further push their living standards and be better off.

In Condensation, if the overall judgement of if the rising prices have impacted standard of living is to be stated, it would rather be a Multifaceted ruling. It is because if we consider the aspect of the basic amenities as a fundamental element determining standard of living, then although the population has to spend an increased proportion of their income, they can optimistically maintain their standard of living by positively availing all the necessary facilities, however leaving a very grim scope to push it further. Now, if the individual is gratified and is at ease with his current standard of living, then the impact of inflation shall be considerably impotent in his perspective. However, for individuals who aim at pushing their standard of living, will more or less be drained of his income in maintaining their current state of standard of living and will have to face significant hurdle in pushing it further for betterment, and thus inflation in his perspective shall be of considerable detriment. Thus, in almost every dimension of the verdict, high inflation rate is causing significant hurdles and hardships for the population, although its magnitude of impact is divergently felt, in accordance to the respective perceptions of individuals.

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